

Application of xanthine functionalized resin in speciation of chromium in natural water

Debasish Banerjee and Arabinda K. Das*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Golapbag, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : arabindakdas@rediffmail.com; debasishbanerjebu@yahoo.com

Fax : 91-342-2557938

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Abstract : Separation and preconcentration of two forms of chromium viz. Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in natural water was carried out applying a resin containing xanthine moiety anchored onto polystyrene-divinylbenzene (8%) by azo (-N=N-) function. The maximum exchange capacity of Cr^{III} was found to be 0.6718 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 6.5 and that for Cr^{VI} was 1.1324 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 1.0. The sorption of both Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} onto resin follows a second order kinetics with rate constant values of 0.047 and 0.410 mmol⁻¹ min⁻¹ for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} respectively. The two species Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} are eluted completely by 3 M and 4 M HCl respectively. The detection limits of 4.3 and 5.1 ng ml⁻¹ for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were achieved. The optimum flow rate, sample breakthrough volume of column operation for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} species were found to be 1.2 ml min⁻¹ and 3000 ml respectively. Finally the developed method using this resin was applied for determination of these two species in synthetic binary mixtures, natural water samples and validated comparing with results using previously developed method.

Keywords : Solid phase extraction, chelating resin, xanthine, chromium(III) and (VI).

Recently interest has been developed towards the speciation study of various trace metal ions dispersed in the environment because some elements even in the trace or ultratrace level have different physiological and biological functions and different chemical properties. For example hexavalent chromium compounds are essentially carcinogenic¹ and toxic whereas trivalent chromium compounds are potentially nontoxic. As bioavailability of a metal species is controlled by the change of chemistry due to different oxidation states the toxicity behaviour due to that chemical species also varies. Thus determination of only the total chromium in the environmental sample is not sufficient to elucidate the biochemical as well as toxicological functions in the environmental chemistry; speciation study is also very important.

Generally combustion of fossil fuel, incineration of municipal wastes, metal plating industry and different industrial process contributes to the emission and dispersion of chromium in the environment². The hexavalent and trivalent chromium species get reduced with naturally occurring enzymes to different intermediates which contributes to the cytotoxicity, genotoxicity and carcinogenicity in living being³. Recently toxic effects of hexavalent chromium on microorganism, plant and human health have been studied by several authors⁴.

Speciation study of chromium is controlled by some factors like redox potential, pH of the medium etc. Thus above pH 7 Cr^{III} predominates and below pH 6 Cr^{VI} is the dominating species⁵. Chromium is present in natural water mainly as chromate and cationic hydroxo complexes^{6,7}. Therefore determination of individual species of chromium is critical in natural, waste or drinking water⁸. For speciation study separation of one specific form in low concentration of chromium is usually carried out by sorption⁹, solvent extraction¹⁰ and coprecipitation¹¹ followed by instrumental analysis. The second form is measured after it has been reduced or oxidized as the residual chromium content of the solution using the same technique¹². At present for the purpose of extraction and preconcentration of trace metal ion solid phase extraction is used widely.

Polyimine detata sorbent¹³, anionic solid exchanger¹⁴, solid phase resin^{15,16}, biosorption¹⁷ have been applied for separation and preconcentration of chromium species. Nevertheless the reports of pH dependent speciation followed by selective elution of different species of chromium are scarce^{13,16,18}.

The present work describes the separation and preconcentration of two forms of chromium, viz. Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} by using a resin containing xanthine as func-

tional group anchored by azo (-N=N-) group onto polystyrene-divinyl benzene followed by determination of these two species using flame atomic absorption spectrometry.

Structure of xanthine resin

Results and discussion

The sorption behaviour of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} was studied using the batch technique and the results are shown in Fig. 1. The absorption capacity of Cr^{III} onto the resin increases with increasing pH of the medium reaching a maximum value of $0.6718 \text{ mmol g}^{-1}$ at pH 6.5, whereas the reverse was found in case of Cr^{VI} where maximum value of $1.1324 \text{ mmol g}^{-1}$ was found at pH 1.0. The resin gets protonated at lower pH and subsequently binds Cr^{VI} which is also supported by very low exchange of Cr^{III} at lower pH. On the other hand at high pH may be due to chelation by the azo function the xanthine moiety the Cr^{III} species get absorbed. Thus separation of these two species of chromium from each other is possible merely by pH adjustment.

Fig. 1. Exchange capacity in mmol g^{-1} for chromium(III) and chromium(VI) on xanthine resin at different pH : (■) Cr^{VI} , (▲) Cr^{III} .

The effects of different eluents towards desorption of these two species are presented in Table 1. Complete desorption of Cr^{III} takes place by 3 M HCl and that of Cr^{VI} is achieved by 4 M HCl.

Table 1. Desorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} by different eluents

Eluents (M)	% Recovery	
	Cr^{III}	Cr^{VI}
0.01 HCl	11.2	8.6
0.1 HCl	16.3	10.2
0.2 HCl	20.8	18.6
0.5 HCl	28.4	30.2
1.0 HCl	42.6	40.8
2.0 HCl	78.7	81.6
3.0 HCl	100.6	92.6
4.0 HCl	100.1	100.3
0.01 HNO_3	18.1	22.7
0.1 HNO_3	20.6	24.4
1.0 HNO_3	71.3	78.2
2.0 HNO_3	99.6	93.4

Kinetic parameters : According to Frost and Pearson¹⁹ the rate of metal ion exchange onto a chelating resin is controlled by a second order kinetic equation. Turse and Rieman²⁰ determined the rate of exchange of metal ions onto chelating resin by the following equation :

$$\ln Z = 2kQ_0(Q_0 - Q_\infty)t/Q_\infty$$

where $Z = [(Q_0(Q_0 - 2Q_\infty) + Q_0Q_\infty)]/Q_0(Q_\infty - Q_0)$ and Q_0 = amt (mmol) of metal ion exchanged.

At optimum pH of 6.5 for Cr^{III} and 1.0 for Cr^{VI} , the values of other parameters are :

Q_∞ = maximum capacity at equilibrium (0.67 and 1.13) and

Q_0 = amount of chelating sorbent in terms of mmol of Na^+ exchanged after 24 h (1.17 and 1.17).

A plot of $\ln Z$ vs t should be a linear plot passing through origin for a second order kinetics and S is given by $S = 2kQ_0(Q_0 - Q_\infty)/Q_\infty$. The values of S and K (mmol min^{-1}) are 0.0818, 0.0318 and 0.047 and 0.4101 respectively. The linear nature of plot of the $\ln Z$ vs t supports the second order kinetics for the reaction.

Sample breakthrough volume and lower limit of detection : The plot of percent sorption against sample volume is shown in Fig. 2. It was found that percent sorption drops with sample volume after the 4000 ml mark.

Upto sample volume of 4000 ml the recovery is greater than 99.5% and it gives a preconcentration factor of 400. This reflects the enhanced accessibility of chelating sites into the resin (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Sample breakthrough volume curve for sorption of chromium(III) and chromium(VI) (■) Cr^{III}, (▲) Cr^{VI}

The sensitivity of a resin towards metal ion of interest is characterized by lower concentration below which quantitative sorption by chelating matrix is not perceptibly seen. Using the optimum condition of sorption (pH, sample volume and flow rate) detection limit of 4.3 and 5.1 ng cm⁻³ for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were achieved. This lower value of detection limit suggests the higher sensitivity of the final resin. The optimum condition of sorption and desorption for column operation is presented in Table 2.

The flow rate of the sample affects the retention of both Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} on the resin. Therefore the effect of flow rate of sample solution was examined with the column adjusted under optimum condition of pH and eluent. The flow rate higher than 1.2 ml min⁻¹ causes a decrease in percentage of sorption. So a flow rate of 1.2 ml min⁻¹ were chosen for column operation as optimum flow rate.

Separation study of 2 µg ml⁻¹ of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from several binary mixtures was carried out (Table 3). The presence of 1000 fold excess of various metal ions did not interfere except arsenate and molybdate for Cr^{VI}. Elution of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} was achieved almost 100% using suitable eluents already described. Hence attempts were made to separate Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from each other from natural water samples.

Table 2. Separation of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in binary synthetic mixtures

No of observations	Amount taken (µg)	Amount found ^a (µg)	% Error
1	Cr ^{III} 10	Cr ^{III} 9.80 ± 0.3	2.0
	Cr ^{VI} 10	Cr ^{VI} 10.25 ± 0.2	2.5
2	Cr ^{III} 1	Cr ^{III} 0.97 ± 0.03	3.0
	Cr ^{VI} 10	Cr ^{VI} 9.90 ± 0.08	1.0
3	Cr ^{III} 1	Cr ^{III} 0.95 ± 0.07	5.0
	Cr ^{VI} 1	Cr ^{VI} 0.97 ± 0.02	3.0
4	Cr ^{III} 10	Cr ^{III} 10.21 ± 0.03	2.1
	Cr ^{VI} 1	Cr ^{VI} 0.96 ± 0.08	4.0
5	Cr ^{III} 100	Cr ^{III} 103.20 ± 0.03	3.2
	Cr ^{VI} 10	Cr ^{VI} 9.80 ± 0.08	2.0
6	Cr ^{III} 10	Cr ^{III} 10.40 ± 0.03	4.0
	Cr ^{VI} 100	Cr ^{VI} 97.60 ± 0.08	2.4
7	Cr ^{III} 100	Cr ^{III} 103.10 ± 0.03	3.1
	Cr ^{VI} 1	Cr ^{VI} 0.98 ± 0.08	2.0
8	Cr ^{III} 1	Cr ^{III} 1.05 ± 0.03	5.0
	Cr ^{VI} 100	Cr ^{VI} 98.20 ± 0.08	1.8

^aAverage of five determinations

Analytical characteristics : The sensitivity of a resin towards metal ion of interest is characterized by lower concentration below which quantitative sorption by chelat-

Table 3. Separation of 2 µg ml⁻¹ each of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from several binary mixtures in sample of 50 ml

Foreign ions ^a	% Recovery	
	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}
Hg ^{II}	98.3	97.7
Ag ^I	101.6	98.9
Fe ^{III}	96.7	99.6
Cu ^{II}	97.1	100.5
Co ^{II}	98.8	99.1
Mn ^{II}	90.8	100.8
Na ^I	99.7	101.2
K ^I	102.1	98.9
Ca ^{II}	98.2	99.2
Ba ^{II}	101.2	97.7
Zn ^{II}	97.2	99.4
MnO ₄ ²⁻	93.2	90.7
PO ₄ ³⁻	98.9	90.6
VO ₃	91.4	97.7
AsO ₄ ³⁻	92.1	89.7
MoO ₄ ²⁻	98.6	83.2
WO ₄ ²⁻	100.1	99.8

^aEach ion added was 1000-fold excess

ing matrix is not perceptibly seen. Using the optimum condition of sorption (pH, sample volume and flow rate) detection limit of 4.3 and 5.1 ng ml⁻¹ for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were achieved. The RSD values (%) for determination of Cr^{III} in real water samples for station 1, station 2 and station 3 are 2.9 ± 0.1, 3.1 ± 0.1 and 2.8 ± 0.1 respectively. The RSD values (%) for determination of Cr^{VI} in real water samples of station 1, station 2 and station 3 are 2.7 ± 0.1, 2.8 ± 0.1 and 3.2 ± 0.1 respectively.

Applications :

Separation of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in binary synthetic mixtures : Different amounts of each of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were mixed having a total volume of 200 ml and each solution was subjected to column operation under optimum conditions. Another portion of 100 ml solution was adjusted to pH 1.0 and passed through the preconditioned column to absorb Cr^{VI} in the column and eluted out by 4 M HCl. Now another volume of 100 ml of the binary mixture is adjusted to pH 6.0 and passed through the preconditioned column to absorb Cr^{III} and the successive elution of Cr^{III} was carried out by 3 M HCl. Concentrations of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were measured in respective volume of eluent as mentioned earlier. The results are presented in Table 4.

Analysis of real water samples : The samples from three different points of the tannery industrial waste water of Kolkata were filtered through a 0.45 µm Millipore membrane filter. Taking 500 ml of the filtrate the pH was maintained at 1.0 and the solution was passed through the resin column. In another 500 ml portion of the filtrate pH was maintained at 6.5 and then passed through the column. The retained species i.e. Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} were eluted out respectively by 4 M HCl and 3 M HCl (10 ml in each case) and the concentrations of each species were measured. The concentration of different species present in different natural water samples are presented in Table 4 and the results were compared with results using earlier developed method¹⁶.

Conclusion :

The application of the xanthine resin offers an excellent means for separation and preconcentration of trace Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from complex samples like tannery waste water. The main advantage of the method is that the separation and preconcentration can be achieved by absorption of both the Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} by differing pH of loading followed by successive elution of the species using different eluting agents. The high exchange capacity of the resin and appreciably low detection limit with high sample breakthrough volume makes it capable of preconcentrating trace concentration of chromium species from a large volume of sample and thus establishes a high sensitivity of the method. The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and free from matrix interference of ions normally present in natural, industrial or environmental samples.

Experimental

A GBC Avanta atomic absorption spectrometer was used to measure absorbance using the following conditions for chromium : lamp current 6 mA, wave length 357.9 with nitrous oxide acetylene flame. A 0.45 µm poresize Milipore membrane filter was used for the filtration of water samples. The pH measurements were carried out with a Systronics 362 pH meter. Potassium dichromate and chromium nitrate (both A.R., B.D.H.) were used as provided. The standard solution of Cr^{III} for AAS measurement was obtained from E. Merck (Germany). The solutions of diverse metal ions were prepared from reagents of analytical grade. All other chemicals were of reagent grade. The glass apparatus were soaked in 4 M nitric acid for overnight and cleaned with double distilled water before use.

Preparation of the resin : Air dried polystyrene DVB copolymer (5 g, 30–60 mesh) was swollen in chloroform, then filtered and was nitrated by 25 ml 18 M H₂SO₄ and 10 ml 15 M HNO₃ by stirring at 600 °C for 1 h. After

Table 4. Determination of chromium(III) and chromium(VI) in natural water after separation using the developed technique

Sample no.	Cr ^{III} found using developed method (ng ml ⁻¹) ^a	Cr ^{VI} found using developed method (ng ml ⁻¹) ^a	Cr ^{III} found using method ¹⁶ (ng ml ⁻¹) ^a	Cr ^{VI} found using method ¹⁶ (ng ml ⁻¹) ^a
1	655.7 ± 0.4	432.5 ± 0.6	658.2 ± 0.6	429.8 ± 0.8
2	561.7 ± 0.3	378.9 ± 0.5	562.9 ± 0.4	375.2 ± 0.7
3	418.6 ± 0.4	264.4 ± 0.2	421.7 ± 0.7	265.7 ± 0.6

^aAverage of five determinations.

that reaction mixture was poured in into an ice water mixture, the product was filtered and washed thoroughly with water until free from acid. The nitrated resin was then heated with a mixture of 40 g SnCl₂, 12 M HCl in 50 ml ethanol and refluxed for 20 h at 1200 °C. The precipitated mass was then filtered off and washed with water and then with 2 M NaOH followed by 4 M HCl in order to remove the excess SnCl₂. The amino resin was then diazotised according to the literature procedure²¹. The diazotised resin was then treated with xanthine (3.5 g) in NaOH at 0–5 °C for overnight. The resulting dark brown resin was filtered, washed with double distilled water and dried in air. Finally the resin with 30–60 mesh size was retained for use.

Studies of dependence of sorption on pH : In order to find the sorption ability at different pH a batch equilibration technique was used. 25 ml of the sample solution containing 100 µg ml⁻¹ of metal ion was taken in stoppered glass bottles. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 1–7 with help of HCl or sodium acetate buffer. Then 50 mg of the resin was added to each of the bottles and shaken for 10 h. The resin was filtered, washed with water and sorbed metal ion was eluted by suitable eluting agent and concentration was determined by flame AAS using nitrous oxide-acetylene flame.

Kinetic parameters : To determine the kinetic parameters for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} the metal ion solution (30 ml, 1000 µg ml⁻¹ each) was placed in stoppered bottles adjusted to pH 6 and 1 respectively and shaken. At regular time interval, the solution was filtered and sorbed metal species was eluted with suitable eluent from the resin bead and concentration of metal ion was measured by AAS.

Desorption studies : A portion of 0.1 g of the resin with maximum sorbed species was shaken for 24 h with various eluting agents viz. 0.01–4 M HCl, 0.01–2 M HNO₃. Then in each case resin was filtered off and concentrations of chromium species was measured at the specified condition.

Column operation : A 120 × 8 mm glass column was used for the present study. A 500 mg portion of the final resin was suspended in double distilled water and the column was packed by passing through the suspension of the resin so that heavier particles occupy the lower half of the column to prevent choking. Then column was washed with double distilled water followed by appropriate buffer solution.

Maximum sample volume upto which quantitative

chromium sorption takes place was determined by passing sample volume over a range of 500–5000 ml containing 200 µg of chromium species of interest through pre-conditioned resin column. The sorbed species were eluted by 10 ml of appropriate eluent. The percent sorption for different sample volumes was determined to find sample breakthrough volume. To optimize the flow rate of analyte for loading, 500 ml of the sample solution of chromium species containing 2 µg ml⁻¹ pH adjusted to optimum level was passed through the column at different flow rate in the range of 0.1–2.0 ml min⁻¹. The percent recovery of the metal ion of interest at different flow rate was determined. Similarly, to optimize the flow rate of elution appropriate eluent was passed through the column containing maximum sorbed chromium species at different flow rate and percent recovery at different flow rate of eluent was determined. Detection limits are crucial for any newly developed method as it gives idea about its sensitivity towards analytes extraction. Studies by passing 400 ml of sample solution through the preconditioned resin bed containing metal ions in the range of 20–150 µg was carried out for this purpose. To study the effect of diverse ions on the sorption and desorption of chromium species on resin, a suitable aliquot containing 2 µg ml⁻¹ with 1000 times excess of diverse ions were allowed to pass through the preconditioned column at flow rate of 0.8 ml min⁻¹. The stripping of the metal ion was carried out by using already optimized eluent in a 10 ml calibrating flask and determined by flame AAS.

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